

High-Reliability Uncooled InGaAlAs Lasers with Unpumped Current Blocking Regions Near Cavity Facets

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Suggested Citation

Huang, J.J.-S., Shen, S.Y., Wang, C.K., Tsai, F., Chen, H.L. & Shyu, C. (2024). High-Reliability Uncooled InGaAlAs Lasers with Unpumped Current Blocking Regions Near Cavity Facets. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 706-711. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).54](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).54)

Abstract:

The facet heating of high-power laser diodes significantly influences device reliability. To mitigate facet temperature, current blocking (CB) regions are employed at both cavity facets of the laser. In this paper, we investigate the device characteristics of uncooled InGaAlAs lasers with CB facets. We observe two types of light versus current (LI) curves and propose corresponding physical models. Our findings demonstrate the high reliability performance of uncooled lasers with proper engineering design and CB process.

Keywords: *Semiconductor laser 1, current-blocking region 2, facet temperature 3, facet heating 4, unpumped window 5, reliability 6, aging 7, ESD 8.*

Introduction

Semiconductor lasers are indispensable components for optical communications. Due to the large conduction band offset (ΔE_c), aluminum-containing material such as InGaAlAs is widely used for uncooled applications (Takemasa, et al., 1999; Okuda et al., 2002). However, care needs to be taken to

prevent aluminum oxidation in order to achieve high reliability of the InGaAlAs laser (Huang et al., 2021; Ikoma et al., 2005; Matsui et al., 2016). Introducing an unpumped region is one plausible remedy to reduce facet heating and suppress aluminum oxidation. Several methods, including SiN_x isolation (Rinner et al., 2003), active region thinning (Shibutani et al., 1987), n-GaAs formation (Hamada et al., 1991), and p-

InGaAs etching (Xu et al., 2006), have been experimented with to form the unpumped region. However, the unpumped region may lead to non-uniform current pumping, thereby affecting the electrical characteristics of the laser. Very few data have been reported on the changes in device characteristics associated with the unpumped region (Sanayeh, 2008; Huang et al., 2019).

To fully quantify the effect of the unpumped CB region, we conduct statistical data analysis and categorize the lasing behaviors. We demonstrate that the threshold kink observed on the LI curve is correlated with the electrical contact of the CB region. Corresponding physical models are presented.

Materials and Methods

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic of the ridge waveguide (RWG) laser structure (Huang et al., 2016). Initially, an n-type indium phosphide (InP) epitaxial layer was grown as the buffer on top of the S-doped n-type InP substrate using metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD). Subsequently, the active region of InGaAlAs multi-quantum well (MQW) was grown to achieve high optical confinement for the RWG structure. The grating layer of InGaAsP was then grown and patterned using holographic techniques to form the distributed feedback (DFB) laser (Huang & Jan, 2017; Huang et al., 2018). Directly on top of the grating layer, the p-InP cladding was overgrown. Finally, the contact layer was formed using heavily-doped p+-InGaAs to establish Ohmic contact with the Ti/Pt/Au p-metal. The laser cavity was cleaved into lengths of 200 μm . To mitigate facet temperature, current blocking (CB) regions were created at both facets by etching the top p-InGaAs layer, with the CB region measuring approximately 10 μm in length.

Two types of laser diodes were fabricated, each featuring a current blocking region (10 μm) on both the front and rear facets. Type A incorporates an Ohmic contact at the current blocking region, whereas Type B incorporates a Schottky contact at the same region.

Figure 1. Schematic of Uncooled InAlGaAs Laser Structure Based on Ridge Waveguide Design. The Current Blocking Regions at Both Facets were Formed by Removing the p-InGaAs Layer

The lasers underwent testing using a human-body-model (HBM) electrostatic discharge (ESD) simulator, adhering to the Telcordia TR-NWT-000870 standard (Telcordia, 1991). The testing setup consisted of a circuit with parameters of 1.5 k Ω resistance and 100 pF capacitance. The chips, mounted on transistor outline (TO) packages, facilitated ESD testing. The ESD probes made contact with the electrical leads of the TO packages, connected to the p- and n-sides of the laser device. During testing, the ground of the ESD tester was connected to the n-side (cathode) of the laser, while the ESD bias was applied to the p-side (anode). The ESD stress voltage ranged from 0.1 kV to 8 kV, allowing observation of the entire evolution of ESD failure morphology. Current versus voltage (IV) measurements were taken before and after each ESD stress to determine the ESD failure threshold. ESD failure was defined as a reverse voltage change exceeding 1 V at a reverse current of 1 μA (Huang et al., 2019).

Results

The typical LI curves of Type-A and Type-B uncooled RWG lasers are depicted in Figures 2(a) and (b), respectively. In Type-A lasers, which feature Ohmic contact, the LI curve

appears linear with no kink, representing normal laser behavior. However, the threshold current (I_{th}) increases at higher temperatures. On the other hand, Type-B lasers, equipped with Schottky contact, exhibit a normal LI curve at 25°C but display a threshold kink at 90°C.

Figure 3 presents the cross-sectional focused ion beam (FIB) scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of Type-A and Type-B lasers. The Type-A laser demonstrates a smooth p-contact interface characteristic of Ohmic contact. Conversely, the Type-B laser exhibits a rough p-contact interface typical of Schottky contact.

Figure 2. Typical LI Curves of the RWG Uncooled Lasers with CB Regions (a) Type A Shows No Kink on the LI Curve, and (b) Type B Exhibits Delayed Lasing Associated with a Kink Near the Threshold Current at High Temperature (90 °C)

To explain the lasing behaviors observed in Figs. 2(a) and (b), we propose the following physical mechanisms, as illustrated in Figs. 4 and 5. Type-A represents normal laser behavior, where lasing occurs above the I_{th} . With Ohmic contact, the carrier density at the CB region is sufficiently high to activate the laser above the I_{th} . As depicted in Fig. 4, the carrier density at the CB

region ranges from medium to high, resulting in low absorption.

Figure 3. Focused Ion Beam Scanning Electron Microscopy Images of the CB Region from (a) a Type A Laser with No Threshold Kink and (b) a Type B Laser with a Threshold Kink at 90 °C

Figure 4. Schematic of a Type A Laser, where the Ohmic Contact Generates Medium to High Carrier Density at the CB Region

Type-B exhibits a threshold kink behavior and delayed lasing. Below the I_{th} , the carrier density is low due to the Schottky contact (as shown in Fig. 5). Consequently, the CB region acts as an optical absorber, leading to a threshold kink and delayed lasing. The laser turn-on occurs at a higher injection current compared to a normal laser. At high injection currents, the increasing photon density in the center region can reduce absorption, allowing the entire cavity gain to surpass the threshold.

Figure 5. Schematic of a Type B Laser, where the Schottky Contact Generates Low Carrier Density at the CB Region

Table 1 summarizes the physical mechanisms of Type-A and Type-B lasers. Our model suggests that delayed lasing is likely attributable to optical losses resulting from absorption in the weakly pumped CB region.

Table 1. Physical Mechanisms of Type-A and Type-B Lasers

	Type-A	Type-B
Below I_{th}	CB region has medium to high carrier density and low absorption	CB has low carrier density and high optical absorption
Above I_{th}	Normal laser turn-on with Ohmic contact at the CB region	Increasing photon density in the center region can bleach the absorption

Figure 6 shows the aging plot of uncooled InGaAlAs lasers (with CB regions at the facets), where the operating current is recorded over aging time. All lasers exhibited robust reliability performance after 5000 hours of aging under constant power stress (85°C, 9mW). There was very little change in operating current after 5000 hours of aging.

Table 2 displays the HBM ESD thresholds of the uncooled lasers with and without the CB. The ESD thresholds meet Telcordia specifications (>500V) in both cases (Telcordia, 1991; DeChiaro et al., 1992; Huang et al., 2007; Huang et al., 2017). The laser with the CB region shows a higher ESD threshold attributed to the

reduction in facet temperature of the unpumped CB region.

Figure 6. Aging Plot of High-Speed Uncooled InGaAlAs RWG Lasers. All Lasers Showed Stable Operating Current under Constant Power Stress at 85°C, 9mW over 5000hr

Table 2. Electrostatic Discharge Threshold of Uncooled InGaAlAs Lasers under Forward and Reverse Bias. The ESD Thresholds with and without the CB are Compared

	Forward HBM ESD threshold	Reverse HBM ESD threshold
CB	+7000V	-2300V
No-CB	+6000V	-2000V

Conclusion

We have studied the device characteristics of uncooled InGaAlAs RWG lasers with and without current blocking regions near the cavity facets. The CB region can help improve the ESD performance. Two types of LI curves are observed in the presence of CB regions. Type-A exhibits a normal LI curve with medium to high carrier density at the CB due to Ohmic contact, while Type-B displays a threshold kink and delayed lasing at 90°C when the CB region has Schottky contact. With a good understanding of the CB region, we can fabricate high-reliability

uncooled lasers with proper engineering design and process.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. S-L. Lee (National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, NTUST, Taipei, Taiwan) for helpful discussions. The authors also extend their gratitude to Ashley Huang (UC, Davis, CA) and Shannon Huang (UCLA, Los Angeles, CA) for proofreading the manuscript.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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